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Research Article

**STUDY OF THE PATIENT HAVE DIABETES AND CORONA
VIRUS BOTH THE MAYO HOSPITAL LAHORE**¹Dr Ifra Ali, ²Dr Aashir Jamal, ³Dr Ibraheem Ahmad¹DHQ Sahiwal²Allied Hospital Faisalabad³Sial Hospital Qadir Abas Road Ali Pur Chattha**Article Received:** August 2020 **Accepted:** September 2020 **Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

The covid 19 becomes a great pandemic. It is a disease that covers the all over the world. It covers the entire world the patients who have covid 19 have more chances of a death. It is observed that the covid 19 is spreading like a fire in the whole world. It starts from the developed country china. China is the no 1 in the technology. This panademic starts from the china city Wuhan from a research it is observed that this disease spread in the meat street. From one study it is observed that the this study this disease come from the eating of mices. It covers our entire world. The developed countries are not able to recover this panademic. From a study it is observed that the over the millions of people effected from this disease in the entire world. It is also observed that the it covers over the millions of peoples. It is also observed that the millions of people are died due to this life taking disease it is observed that the patient who have covid 19 has ability to transfer it to another person through sneezing soughing and by using touching. The test had been performed in the laboratory to find this covid 19 if the result of a patient becomes positive then the patients had shifted to the quarantine session. Like the whole world it covers also the Pakistan when the cases start reporting in the Pakistan then the full lockdown exist in the Pakistan due to which no one able to go outside. The quarantine center also starts in Pakistan. The using of the sanitizer becomes important or compulsory in the entire world. The quarantine session also exist in the center Lahore. The main goal of a mayo hospital Lahore is to heal the patients suffering from type 1 diabetes and the covid 19 both. It's a great challenge for the mayo hospital by the grace of the GOD the mayo hospital Lahore outcomes this challenge and beats the both panademic diseases.

KEYWORDS: Mayo hospital Lahore, type 1 diabetes, covid 19, life taking diseases, overcoming challenges, whole world covers.

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INTRODUCTION:

During this pandemic the both patients have the type 1 diabetes and the covid 19 reported. It is the great challenge of a mayo hospital Lahore to overcome these two pandemics as both. The corona virus means the covid 19 have the disease of a breathing that starts in a china city called Wuhan. It is observed that this disease spreads like a fire in all the entire world it does not gave time to the world. It spreads through coughing sneezing and by touching. So for the avoidance of this the hand shake become banned in the entire world. It is also observed that the patient have type 1 diabetes and corona virus how we overcome this two pandemic in a one patient. So this study is become a great issue. It is observed that the type 1 diabetes is a type of diabetes in which patient have higher level of sugar and the glucose level. It is observed that the form 1 diabetes also takes the life of many patients the entire world. It is also observed that the covid 19 called corona virus also covers the all the entire world. And takes the life of a millions of a people. If these two diseases exist in a one patient so what we did let's see it's a great challenge for the mayo hospital Lahore. It is also observed that the patient have the covid 19 and the type 1 diabetes how we will overcome it. This study is performed in the mayo hospital Lahore on the month of July in mayo hospital Lahore. It is observed that the 30 percent of young is died due to this corona virus and about all the aged died from the corona virus some aged people have the strong immune system have stayed in this word it is observed that the every third person of the world have the corona virus. Different sops have developed in this regard it is a great stanza have the prevention is better than the cure. It is also observed that the patients have the serious corona virus we gave them a vantiilation it is observed that the on the ventilation they don't lost hope and cure from this disease different disease like the social distancing lock down avoid hand shaking have been observed in this regard. It is observed that the patient have the covid 19 and the type 1 diabetes we have the cureness of this diseases like inhaled therapy like optional use of the filter. It is observed that the Russia had made the vaccine of this pandemic and the result become positive for the usage of this vaccine and the patient start cureness from this disease.

METHODOLOGY:

For the cureness of this two life taking disease we used the following methods that helps patient to provide them a great strongness in the immune system and have the strongness two fights with these two diseases. The first therapy that we used a is called this regard is called the inhaled therapy in

this therapy the ultra-sonic device for the inhalation we used it gives the deep breath to the patient so from this the patient feels good and start healing this device had been used in the home hospital and also on other places easily. The other method used in this therapy is called the device called the multi-sonic infra control this device is used to provide the medicine delivery in the body it is observed that the patient have the covid 19 is not have in there sense so the delivery of the medicine is not become possible as it acts as soon as a possible. By using the multi-sonic infra control the delivery of the medicine become easy. In the mayo hospital Lahore we used the method of the plasma transplant that helps in a strong ness of the immune system and the patient bodies have become the ability to get the result.

RESULT:

In mayo hospital the corona virus ward has been making. The quarantine session had been observed so that the patient does not have the ability to spread this disease but using the sneezing or coughing and by using touching different devices used for the inhale and the exhale of the air so that the patient could become easy to breath. In easy world the lungs cancer exist in this regard. We also used the device that gives the patient to proper observance of the medicine. The device used for the inhalation of the air called it the ultra-sonic. The devise used for the proper observance of the medicine is called the multi-sonic infra control and the device used for the proper monitor is called the ventilator we also used the another therapy is called the plasma therapy.

DISCUSSION:

It is observed that this the two pandemic acts on the body how it takes the life of a patient it is a life taking disease it is observed that the. By using the multi-sonic infra control the delivery of the medicine become easy. In the mayo hospital Lahore we used the method of the plasma transplant that helps in a strong ness of the immune system and the patient bodies have become the ability to get the result. . We also used the device that gives the patient to proper observance of the medicine. The device used for the inhalation of the air called it the ultra-sonic.

CONCLUSION:

It is observed that this disease spreads like a fire in all the entire world it does not gave time to the world. It's spreading through coughing sneezing and by touching. So for the avoidance of this the hand shake become banned in the entire world. It is also observed that the patient have type 1 diabetes and corona virus how we overcome this two pandemic in a one patient. The test had been performed in the laboratory to find this covid 19 if

the result of a patient becomes positive then the patients had shifted to the quarantine session. Like the whole world it covers also the Pakistan when the cases start reporting in the Pakistan then the full lockdown exist in the Pakistan due to which no one able to go outside.

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